

The multi-search system E-CONNECT, a new type of database systems¹

Introduction

This search system demonstrates how a complex database system can be created with pure HTML and javascript. Fields of web forms serve in this system to store the database, which is quite unusual. In general, form fields are only used for the temporary storage of very limited amounts of data, not for the permanent storage of larger amounts. Javascript here is used to manage and search the databases contents. In addition, it is simplified and doesn't contain any unnecessary details. This makes the multi-search system a unique exception. I am not yet aware of a similarly developed system. Creating a database system is a difficult undertaking normally reserved for IT specialists, and not for a non-IT specialist, as I am. Special hardware and software are required, which I don't have. A complex database system with pure HTML and Javascript seems to be a mistake. In addition, there are reservations against javascript, which seems to be suitable only for smaller programming tasks. Additionally, an open access to the source code, as javascript offers, is disadvantageous, too. In the nineties these things still set narrow limits for the use of form fields and javascript. That has recently changed. Capacity and speed of computers have improved. Now even larger amounts of data of around 12 MB can be easily saved in form fields.

ASEZA

The Multisuchsystem E-Connect consists of several different systems. It starts with the search form of ASEZA, a search system for electronic journals (fig. 1).How is it constructed?

Fig. 1 ASEZA. Search System for electronic journals

A list of about 40000 journal titles serves as data basis. This list supplemented by terms of themes and library holdings is deposited in a hidden text field:

input type=hidden name=area value="List of journals.....">

The list is included with quotation marks. As consequence there must be no quotation

¹ <http://www.multisuchsystem.de/aseza.html>

marks within the list.

The following figure shows how the list is deposited in a hidden text field of the website *such1.htm*:

```
<htm>
<body onload="such0()">
<script src="contents4c.js">
</script>
<form name=forma><input type=hidden name=area value="
>027.7=inf=*FREI
>19&20=artm=*FREI
>291=artm=*FREI
>391=artm=*FREI
>3C ON LINE=comp=*TIB*FHR*G*RE*UBPO*UBRO >3C TIC=econ=inf=*FREI
>3D RESEARCH=comp=*TIB*AA*FHR*G*RE*UBPO*UBRO
>4OR=econ=math=*TIB*RE*AA*FHR*G*UBPO*UBRO >A CONTRARIO=socallg=*FREI
>A RAYONS OUVERTS=inf=*FREI
.....
..... " >
```

Fig. 2 Website *such1.htm* with list of journals

It is certainly interesting how this list is accessed.

When starting a search by submitting the search form, ASEZA creates an address line with selected or entered values. For example: If library *RE* (UB Regensburg) is selected and *clima* as search term is entered, the following address line is automatically created:

file:///D:/EEZB/such1.htm?TI=clima&t=&bib=RE&l=de

That means that the website *such1.htm* is opened with these values; *TI=* means title and starts a title search function with the entered value *clima*. *such1.htm* is connected with the javascript code in *contents4s.js*. On loading *such1.htm* the function *such0()* is activated (*onload="such0()"*), as shown in fig.2. The function determines the term *TI* and accordingly starts the function *such()*.² This function searches journals with the entered value *clima*.

The founded titles are written out with hyperlinks to EZB³, Google Scholar or Google and thematic terms. (The journal title is connected with the EZB.)

```
ADVANCES IN CLIMATE CHANGE RESEARCH (Google Scholar) (Google) globw geo ene RE FREI
AIR QUALITY AND CLIMATE CHANGE (Google Scholar) (Google) env ene
CARBON AND CLIMATE LAW REVIEW (Google Scholar) (Google) env
CLIMACTERIC (Google Scholar) (Google) gyn med RE
CLIMATE & DEVELOPMENT (Google Scholar) (Google) globw ene
CLIMATE AND ELECTRICITY ANNUAL (Google Scholar) (Google) ene
CLIMATE CHANGE ECONOMICS (Google Scholar) (Google) globw geo ene
CLIMATE DYNAMICS (Google Scholar) (Google) geo klima phys RE
CLIMATE LAW (Google Scholar) (Google) globw geo env RE
CLIMATE OF THE PAST (Google Scholar) (Google) geo FREI
CLIMATE POLICY (Google Scholar) (Google) globw adm env geo klima pol
CLIMATE RESEARCH (Google Scholar) (Google) geo geog env klima phys FREI-(ALTERALS4JAHRE )
CLIMATIC
.....
.....: 34 Treffer
```

2 The code therefor is: *if(aa[0].match(/TI=/))such()*;

3 Elektronische Zeitschriftenbibliothek Regensburg

If clicking on a thematic term. f.e. *globw*, another address line is created:
file:///D:/EEZB/such1.htm?Schlag==globw&b=RE

In this case according to the term *Schlag* a function for searching journals by keyword is activated and finally all titles found are written out.

In similar way the processes work in the literature management program

Contents-Linking IIa

Fig. 4 Contents-Linking IIa

The literature management system *Contents-Linking IIa* is connected with two databases: a database of journal titles and a database of about 40000 article records. The database of journal titles is deposited in a text field of the website *suchcont1a.htm*. The database of article records is deposited in a text field of the website *suchcont1b.htm*.⁴ *suchcont1a* contains the same journals as ASEZA, plus 16000 PubMed titles. In addition there is a short title list of all journals contained in *suchcont1b* and a list of all used keywords.

if you are searching for titles by keyword *geotechnics*, the created adress line is:
file:///D:/EEZB/suchcont1a.htm?Schlag==geot=&b=

<p>CANADIAN GEOTECHNICAL J (Google Scholar) (WorldCat) COLD REGIONS SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY (Google Scholar) (WorldCat) COMPUTERS AND GEOTECHNICS (Google Scholar) (WorldCat) SOIL DYNAMICS AND EARTHQUAKE ENGINEERING (Google Scholar) (WorldCat) SOIL MECHANICS AND FOUNDATION ENGINEERING (Google Scholar) (WorldCat) FREI- SOILS AND FOUNDATIONS (Google Scholar) (WorldCat) FREI- TRANSPORT IN POROUS MEDIA (Google Scholar) (WorldCat) Cold Reg Sci Technol (Google) (WorldCat)</p> <p>17 Treffer 2 Treffer in Aufsatzdatenbank (Titel fett geschrieben)</p>

Fig. 5 Journal titles found by keyword *geotechnics*.

4 The names for files, functions etc. are not unified, they are the result of several years developing

suchcont1a.htm is combined with the source code in *contents3.js*. On loading *suchcont1a* the same function *such0()* is activated as in ASZA. Titles are written out (fig.5). Titles which are also found in the database of article records are written bold. That is achieved by an additional search in the short title list of all journals contained in the article database.

The bold written titles are hyperlinks which generate the following javascript code:

```
javascript:b="";iss="";window.location='suchcont1b.htm?Zze='+SOIL MECHANICS AND FOUNDATION ENGINEERING+'&IS='+iss+'&SS='+geot+'&b='+b
```

In this case according to the term *Zze* the function *such1a()* for searching the journal *soil mechanics and foundation engineering* in the article database *suchcont1b.htm* is activated. All found articles are written in short format (fig.6). When clicking upon *zur Vollanzeige* the record is shown in full format (fig.7). This hyperlink is bound in the following javascript code:

```
javascript>window.location='suchcont1a.htm?einzeln1&'+1964 z=soil mechanics and foundation engineering*construction of houses on pile foundations in salavat*v. a. komlevg. s. kolesnik*,1,2 ,1964,*sw: ';
```

1964 soil mechanics and foundation engineering
 construction of houses on pile foundations in salavat
 a. komlevg. s. kolesnik
 ,1,2 ,1964,
 SW:
[zur Vollanzeige](#)

Fig. 6 A Record in short format

The full text form is written by adding some hyperlinks whose values were found in the journals database (fig. 7);

soil mechanics and foundation engineering
construction of houses on pile foundations in salavat
a. komlevg. s. kolesnik
,1,2 ,1964,
SW:
[SOIL MECHANICS AND FOUNDATION ENGINEERING](#) +

[\(Google Scholar\)\(Google\) \(Worldcat\) SW: CONST ENG GEO GEOT](#)

Fig.7 A Record in full format

Contents-Linking IIb

Another option to deposit data into a form field is to use a visible multi-line text field. There the data are deposited between `<textarea name=area>` and `</textarea>`. This is applied in the literature management system *Contents-Linking IIb* which is constructed by several frames. The databases for journals and records are distributed over several frames, very small looking (fig. 8). *Contents-Linking IIb* is a more complex system than *Contents-Linking IIa*, because it includes besides a search system for electronic journals and a literature management system a multiple linking system. Fig. 8 shows in the

right window the search form for searching journals by keyword. In the left window you see the main form for searching or displaying journals and records.⁵ For example if you enter a search term into the input field above, you get optionally article records or journal titles or both as result.

Fig. 8 Contents-Linking IIb

Let us see how hyperlinks work in this system! If you open a section of the journal titles by clicking upon the button *Zeitschriften alphabetisch* you get an alphabetically list of journals. Fig.9 shows a section of it. These journals are contained in the database of article records. The plus sign means, that they are also found in the journals database.

[G ITAL CARDIOL](#) +
[G ITAL DERMATOL VENEREOL](#) +
[G ITAL MED LAV](#) +
[G ITAL MED LAV ERGON](#) +
[ITAL NEFROL](#) +
[GAC MED MEX](#) +
[GAN TO KAGAKU RYOHO](#) +
[GASTRIC CANCER](#) +
[GASTROENTEROL CLIN NORTH AM](#) +
[GASTROENTEROL HEPATOL](#) +

Fig. 9 List of journals contained in the database of article records

All titles are hyperlinks. When clicking upon one, the following javascript code is created:

```
javascript:top.links.oben.document.forma2.area3.value='G ITAL  
CARDIOL';top.links.oben.document.forma2.starte2.click()
```

There are 2 commands which define the frame, the form, one text field and the button *starte2* which is to be clicked. *top.links.oben* means the main search form of the system. In its second form *forma2* the text field *area3* is to be entered by the value *G ITAL CARDIOL* (=journal title). In the next command *starte2* is clicked, defined by *onclick="such2()"*, which means that function *such2()* is starting for searching journals by keyword.

⁵ The main form is located in *ArticleSab.htm* connected with *contents1.js*

form *forma2* is a part of the main search form and contains a number of hidden input elements. Fig. 10 shows a section of them.

```
<input name="area3" value="" type="hidden"><input value="" name="area3a" type="hidden"><input  
name="starte3" value="" onclick="such2()" type="hidden"><input name="starte3a" value=""  
onclick="such2a()" type="hidden"><input name="starte3b" value=""
```

Fig. 10 Hidden input elements in *forma2*

Nearly almost hyperlinks have to be achieved by this manner. Search results are written in a frame other than the frame in which the javascript code is located. The code cannot be accessed directly, but only by these commands via hidden form elements.

Conclusion

I don't want to go into more details on other options of this system, f.e. on the interesting multiple linking system (*Multipler Linksystem*) and on the import of reports from relevant databases. Only the possibility of depositing databases in form fields and editing them with javascript should be shown here. I am aware that there may be even better solutions for tasks in this area, which are unknown to me. The systems shown here are not definitive systems, although they work excellently, but are rather in an experimental stage. This applies also to the other literature management systems not discussed here: *Contents Literaturverwaltung* I and II, which represent further developments.

With this presentation, I would like to address interested people who want to take a closer look at this project and can perhaps contribute to a more general spread. Because I am alone and not a specialist and at an advanced age. I cannot do this.

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Die elektronische Bibliothek. München: de Gruyter 1999
2. erw. Aufl. 2001

Journal articles

Linkssysteme: Einfache und effektive Verfahren mittels Webformularen

J HEHL - Information Wissenschaft und Praxis, 2005 - De Gruyter

SFX und die Linkssysteme im Multisuchsystem E-Connect : ein Vergleich

Hehl, Johannes. - In: Bibliotheksdienst, ISSN 0006-1972, Bd. 39 (2005), S. 0932-0945

Die Linkssysteme des Multisuchsystems E-Conect : Ausatzrecherche mit Zugang zum Volltext und zu Verbundkatalogen

Hehl, Hans. - In: Bibliotheksdienst, ISSN 0006-1972, Bd. 37 (2003), S. 0774-0789

Der Recherchedienst Ingenta und seine Erweiterung durch das Linkssystem Ingenta-Link

Hehl, Hans. - In: Bibliothek, ISSN 0341-4183, Bd. 26 (2002), S. 169-175

Das Linkssystem Math-Link : Verknüpfung von MathDatabase mit elektronischen Aufsätzen und Verbundkatalogen

Hehl, Hans. - In: Bibliotheksdienst, ISSN 0006-1972, Bd. 35 (2001), S. 1344-1350

Die digitale Bibliothek in der Praxis

Hehl, Hans. - In: Bibliothek, ISSN 0341-4183, Bd. 24 (2000), S. 336-341

Internet: Multisuchsystem E-Connect (<http://www.multisuchsystem.de>)

In this you find further comprehensive demonstrations and documentations of the separate systems of the multi-search system.